

BREAKING FRONTIERS IN SUSTAINABLE AND CIRCULAR BIOCOMPOSITES WITH HIGH PERFORMANCE.

For more info
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B right bio-based solutions
I nnovation BioC application
O ptimised manufacturing process
N ovel BioC-end products
T ailor-made materials compositions
I ntegral sustainability
E nvironmentally friendly
R euse and recycling

WHAT?

BIONtier seeks to develop novel bio-based materials, which is at the forefront of material science today.

WHERE?

Our project activities take place across Europe, consortium partners from **12 countries** work together.

WHEN?

Following a Kick-Off Meeting in October 2024, BIONtier runs for a total of 3 years and ends in September 2027.

ABOUT US:

- BIONtier is a **3-year project** (2024-2027) led by FORTH – Foundation for research and technology-Hellas
- BIONtier applications are designed for easy manufacturing, testing, and recycling, using **advanced bioconstruction processes** to optimise performance and durability.
- By uniting major industries, **SMEs, research centers, and universities**, BIONtier accelerates the time-to-market for **high-performance bio-based solutions**.
- This collaboration **strengthens the EU's position** as a leader in the **bioeconomy and sustainable technology industry**, with positive industrial and societal benefits, contributing to a more eco-friendly economy.

5 MAJOR OBJECTIVES

SUSTAINABLE AND CIRCULAR DESIGN

INNOVATIVE AND SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS

MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGIES AND PROTOTYPING

SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT AND END-OF-LIFE MANAGEMENT

AWARENESS AND MARKET ADOPTION

BIONtier CONSORTIUM:

MORE INFORMATION:

For more info
Scan here!

www.biontier.eu

BIONtier

BIONtier

Circular
Bio-based
Europe
Joint Undertaking

Cofunded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Bio-based Industries
Consortium

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